

EXISTENTIAL INTERPRETATION OF THE SOCIO- SPIRITUAL ZEITGEIST IN UZBEK AND FRENCH NOVELS (BASED ON THE EXAMPLES OF "THE PLAGUE" BY A. CAMUS AND "BAZAAR" BY KH. DUSTMUHAMMAD)

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the novel "The Plague" by Albert Camus, a prominent representative of 20th-century world literature, and the work "The Market" by Khurshid Dostmuhammad, a prominent example of Uzbek modern literature, in a comparative-typological aspect. The article analyzes the approaches of both writers to the concepts of human existence, alienation, absurdity, and "boundary situation" (Grenzsituation). The allegorical essence of the images of "Plague" and "Market," their features as a socio-spiritual space are revealed. During the study, the reflection of the philosophy of existentialism in the literary text and the transformations in the psyche of the characters are highlighted in a comparative aspect. This article examines the novel "The Plague" by Albert Camus, a prominent representative of 20th-century world literature, and the work "Bazaar" by Khurshid Dostmuhammad, a prominent example of modern Uzbek literature, in a comparative-typological aspect. The article analyzes the approaches of both authors to the concepts of human existence, alienation, absurdity, and "boundary situation." The allegorical essence of the images of "Plague" and "Market," their features as a socio-spiritual space are revealed. In the course of the research, the reflection of the philosophy of existentialism in the literary text and the transformations in the psyche of the characters are highlighted in a comparative aspect.

Entrance

In the world literary process, the evolution of artistic thinking is always inextricably linked with new philosophical concepts in understanding the essence of man. Modernist

research, observed in the West in the middle of the 20th century and in Eastern (in particular, Uzbek) prose at the end of the century, shifted the focus from external reality to the inner world of man, to the problem of his "existence in being" (Dasein). From this point of view, the study of the typological commonality between Albert Camus's novel "The Plague" (La Peste, 1947), which is considered the manifesto of French existentialism, and Khurshid Dostmuhammad's novel "The Market" (2000), which opened new horizons of socio-psychological prose in Uzbek literature, is of urgent scientific importance. Although both works were created in different socio-historical formations (one in post-war Europe, the other in the transitional period of independence), they unite on a single aesthetic platform in depicting the spiritual crisis and ontological loneliness of man.

If we approach the issue of chronotope (unity of space and time), which is the core of the poetics of a work of art, from a theoretical and historical point of view, we will see that Camus's city of Oran and the market of Dostmuhammad are not just geographical or economic territories. These spaces, in M. Bakhtin's words, are "threshold" chronotopes that test the hero and reveal his essence. Albert Camus, describing the city of Oran, emphasizes that it was "without trees, birds, and souls," indicating that society was in a state of spiritual paralysis before the arrival of the plague [2, 120]. The closure of the city gates is a state of existential "siege," which condemns a person to isolation from the outside world, to solitude with their absurdity.

It is at this point that Khurshid Dostmuhammad's novel "The Market" enters into an original dialogue with Camus's concept. The image of the "Market," created by the writer, is not a local point of sale, but a symbol of totalitarian chaos, "overwhelming the world" [1, 5], conquering the consciousness and spirit of man. If in Camus the siege was imposed from outside (due to an epidemic), then in "The Bazaar" the heroes voluntarily fall into the "siege of desires." Just as the silence and death smell in Oran are terrifying, the continuous noise, dust, and chaotic movement in the Market are tools that separate a person from their "Self." Both spaces are "closed" systems, from which one can physically escape (escape from Oran or return home from the Bazaar), but it is impossible to escape spiritually.

The leading motif in the works is the "border situation" and the manifestation of human choice in it. According to the philosophy of Karl Jaspers, a person forgets themselves in everyday life and realizes their true existence only in the face of the danger of death or severe suffering. In "Plague," this situation creates a risk of death, while in "Market," it creates a risk of being swallowed by mass culture and consumer psychology. Dr. Riye and Fazilbek are characters who are products of two different cultures and two different worldviews, but they are united by "alienation." Although Dr. Riye knows that the absurd (plague) is invincible, he fights against it with the principle of "honesty." His rebellion is an active movement within metaphysical despair.

Fazilbek, the hero of Khurshid Dostmuhammad, is a complex character between Eastern "seclusion" and modern "alienation." His rebellion manifests itself in maintaining silence in a noisy world, refusing "being like everyone" (conformism). Fozilbek's stunned walk amid the market noise, clinging to the truck's side, walking towards the unknown - this is a vivid artistic illustration of M. Heidegger's concept of "abandonment" (Geworfenheit) [3, 115]. It cannot accept market laws because the market turns human relationships into objects of

buying and selling. His cold attitude towards matchmakers and marriage is also a protest against the public sale of private life.

From the point of view of the poetics of the literary text, the stylistic research of Camus and Dostmuhammad, although they have their own differences, serves the unity of purpose. In "The Plague," Camus chooses a dry, emotionless chronicle style; through this, he emphasizes the scale of the tragedy and the fact that evil has become "normal." Khurshid Dostmuhammad effectively uses the "stream of consciousness" method of modernism in "Bozor." Graphic interruptions in the text of the novel, the play of sounds (...or...zor..bozor...), incomplete sentences serve to visually express the fragmentation of the hero's consciousness and the turning of the world into chaos [5, 88]. This method allows the Uzbek reader to intellectually analyze the inner suffering of the hero.

In the process of comparative analysis, the commonality in the system of allegorical images is also clearly visible. Dead rats in "Plague" are material precursors of evil, while "trucks" and "wedding invitations" in "Market" are tools of social pressure that restrict human freedom and put it into standard patterns. In both works, "Others" (in Sartre's words, "Hell is other people") do not understand the hero and try to include him in their ranks, that is, in the ranks of "happy mankurts." Just as the people of Oran have grown accustomed to epidemics and stopped counting on death, the people of Bazaar accept living with lies and desires as a natural phenomenon.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the typological proximity between Albert Camus's "The Plague" and Khurshid Dostmuhammad's "The Market" is not accidental. This is the natural result of humanity's global spiritual crisis of the 20th century, the destruction of traditional values, and the arduous search for self-awareness. The Uzbek writer did not simply copy the experience of Western existentialism, but combined it with the painful points of the transitional society, the national way of thinking, and artistic aesthetics, creating an example of an original national modern novel. "Plague" warns a person about physical and political death, while "Market" is an artistic bell warning a person about spiritual death, that is, mankurtization.

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